

Regional Conference

ACM-W Ahmedabad Regional celebrations held online on 6th December 2021. This was organized by CE-IT department of L.D. College of engineering, ACM Student Chapter and ACM-W India in association with ACM Ahmedabad Professional Chapter and Ganpat University.

The theme was “Artificial Intelligence and Cyber Security for enhancing digital life”

Total 200 participants have attended this conference, 6 papers had been presented on latest technologies, 44 students took part in coding competition held on code chef platform and 5 innovative projects had been demonstrated.

A Review on Discrete Types Of Clusters

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ABSTRACT:

Clustering is an unsupervised machine learning technique for discovering and grouping related data points in huge datasets without regard for the outcome. Clustering (also known as cluster analysis) is a technique for organising data into structures that are easier to comprehend and manipulate. There are a variety of algorithms that use cluster analysis, each with its own process. In this paper discrete type of Clustering has been reviewed such as Hierarchical Density Based Clustering ,k-means clustering,UltraScalable Spectral Clustering and Ensemble Clustering.Moreover, how the selection of structure based on Distribution criteria and even the selection of the initial center cluster creates a great impact on the efficiency is reviewed.The pros and cons of each clustering is discussed in the following of the paper.

INDEX TERMS: Clustering , Big Data , Data Science, types of clusters.

I. INTRODUCTION:

In data science, clustering is a helpful tool. It is a method for determining cluster structure in a data set that is characterised by the highest similarity within a cluster and the least similarity between clusters[1]. Clustering is an unsupervised learning job that seeks to breakdown a dataset into discrete clusters of data objects in order to better understand how it is structured[2]. It is a common technique for statistical data analysis used in many domains, including pattern recognition, image analysis, information retrieval, bioinformatics, data compression, computer graphics, and machine learning, and is a main goal of exploratory data analysis. Partitioning clustering methods, hierarchical clustering methods, density-based clustering methods,grid-based clustering methods, model-based clustering methods, and so on are examples of traditional clustering algorithms[3].

Discrete types of clustering have been discussed in this paper, including Hierarchical Density-Based Clustering, Partition-Based Clustering, Unsupervised K-Means Clustering, Ultrascalable Spectral Clustering and Ensemble Clustering, and a brief discussion on Initial Cluster Center Selection.

Hierarchical Density-Based Clustering provide a hierarchical structure that reflects the order in which groups are merged or divided with a factor of probability density function.

Indeed, the number of items to be clustered has a quadratic lower bound on the computational complexity of hierarchical clustering algorithms. The analysis of such data via hierarchical clustering is becoming more difficult as very huge datasets are generated in an increasing number of real-world application scenarios. Parallelization may improve computational efficiency and widen the applicability of the techniques in certain settings. To achieve this goal, programming models must be employed that allow massive amounts of data to be examined quickly while also ensuring reliability and scalability

as the need for data analysis and database sizes expand. MapReduce is one such programming model that was described in[4].

Partitioning algorithms work by defining an initial number of groups and then iteratively reallocating objects among them until they reach a point of convergence. DBSCAN is an example of Partitioning Algorithm. In DBSCAN, there are two fundamental underlying concepts: density reachability and density connectivity. This aids the algorithm in distinguishing and separating regions of differing densities, resulting in clusters.

Hierarchical Density Clustering and Partition Based Clustering are contrast to each other.

k-means clustering has been extensively investigated in the literature, with numerous extensions, and implemented in a range of substantive fields[5][6]. However, initializations can alter these k-means clustering methods, therefore they must be given a number of clusters ahead of time. The cluster number is generally unknown. Valid indices can be utilized to find a cluster number in this situation because they are designed to be independent of clustering algorithms[7]. Among the many clustering algorithms that have been created, spectral clustering has gotten a lot of interest in recent years because of its potential ability to deal with nonlinearly separable datasets[8][9][10].U-SPEC and U-SENCare the two mainly algorithms used in Ultra Scalable Spectral Clustering and Ensemble Clustering.

In this paper the discrete types of cluster has been reviwed according to their various aspects such as data set size,type of dataset , time complexity, tools used to perform different algorithms. Each clustering have their different type of methodologies their pros and cons which have been discussed in the following part of the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

A. Hierarchical Based Clustering

Clustering methods that are hierarchical are often substantially more computationally intensive than partitioning algorithms. There is an alternative parallelization scheme called MapReduce HDBSCAN* or MR-HDBSCAN* for efficiently applying hierarchical density-based clustering to large datasets using MapReduce, which efficiently computes an approximate clustering hierarchy based on a recursive sampling strategy preliminarily introduced in[11]. There are two main approaches namely Recursive Sampling Approach and HDBSCAN*.

Algorithm of HDBSCAN*:

Requires $\{X=x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}, mpts$
 Output {HDBSCAN* hierarchy}.

1. Calculate the core distances of all the data objects in a dataset X.
2. Create a Minimum Spanning Tree for the Mutual Reachability Graph, Gmreach (the graph does not need to be materialised because the edge weights can be computed on the fly).
3. To produce MSText, extend the MST by adding a "self edge" (i.e., a loop) to each vertex with an edge weight equal to the vertex's core distance, dcore.
4. From MSText, create a dendrogram of the HDBSCAN* hierarchy.
 - a) Initially, all objects are given the same cluster label (the root of the cluster tree).
 - b) Remove edges from MSText in decreasing weight order iteratively.
 - i) Edges of the same weight are removed at +the same time.
 - ii) Cluster labels are assigned to the two connected components that include one vertex of the deleted edge after it is removed. If the component still contains at least one (potentially self) edge, a new cluster label is assigned; otherwise, the object(s) in the component are labelled as noise. FOSC[12], which may automatically extract a "flat" clustering solution based on an optimization criterion, consisting of the most prevalent clusters.

Fig1: Illustration of HDBSCAN[2]

ADVANTAGES:

1. The ability to handle any sort of resemblance or distance with ease.

2. As a result, it can be applied to any attribute type.
3. Algorithms for hierarchical clustering are more versatile.

DISADVANTAGES:

1. Complicated command structures can stifle decision-making.
2. Discrepancies in management at various levels that might obstruct work.
3. Delays in vertical communication between levels and horizontal communication across teams.

Time Complexity:

Time Complexity is $O(n^3)$ where n is number of data points.

B. KMeans CLUSTERING

Partitional approaches work on the assumption that the data set can be represented by finite cluster prototypes with their own objective functions. As a result, partition methods require defining the dissimilarity (or distance) between a point and a cluster prototype. The k-means algorithm is the most well-known and often used partitioning method [13]. Many cluster validity indices for the k-means clustering method have been presented in the literature, including Bayesian information criterion (BIC)[14], Akaike information criterion[15]. The unsupervised k-means (Uk-means) clustering algorithm finds the best number of clusters without any initialization or parameter adjustment. For a long time in the literature, there has always been a severe challenge in the k-means algorithm and its extensions. That is, initializations have an impact on them, and they a priori require a certain number of clusters. The entropy notion is used to design the k-means clustering method with no initializations and automatically find the number of clusters. The notion comes from Yang et al EM .'s algorithm[16].

U-kmeans: The suggested U-k-means algorithm solves the initialization problem by using the number of points as the initial number of clusters. The U-k-means algorithm will eliminate unnecessary clusters during iterations, allowing an optimal number of clusters to be discovered automatically based on the data structure. The advantages of U-k-means are that they are free of initializations and parameters, and they are also robust to variable cluster volumes and shapes, with the number of clusters being automatically determined. On numerous synthetic and actual data sets, the suggested U-k-means algorithm was tested.

Fig2: (a)6-cluster dataset with 50 noisy points
 (b)Final Result after U-kmeans.

ADVANTAGES:

1. Simple to implement
2. Scales to large data Sets
3. Generalize to different type of shape and size of clusters.

DISADVANTAGES:

1. Clustering data of varying size and datasets
2. Clustering Outliers
3. Scaling with number of dimensions

TIME COMPLEXITY:

Time Complexity of Kmeans Algorithm is $O(k+n)$.

C. ULTRA-SCALABLE SPECTRAL CLUSTERING AND ENSEMBLE CLUSTERING

The affinity matrix creation and eigen-decomposition phases of traditional spectral clustering are both time and memory intensive. The affinity matrix takes $O(N2d)$ time and $O(N2)$ memory to generate, while the eigen-decomposition problem takes $O(N3)$ time and $O(N2)$ memory to solve, where N is the data size and d is the dimension[17]. A popular technique for reducing the massive computing cost of spectral clustering is to sparsify the affinity matrix and tackle the eigen-decomposition issue with some sparse eigen-solvers [17].

Although spectral clustering has showed promise in identifying clusters of arbitrary forms from complex data, its $ON3$ time complexity and $ON2$ space complexity severely limit its use in large-scale projects. Various studies sparsified the affinity matrix by considering K -nearest neighbours or -neighbors, and then solved the eigen-decomposition problem with some sparse eigen-solvers [17], however this still necessitates the computation of all the elements in the original affinity matrix.

To deal with large sets of data the U-SPEC algorithm has been proposed. U-SENC algorithm was proposed to integrate multiple U-SPEC's into a unified ensemble clustering framework with the goal of improving clustering robustness while maintaining high efficiency. A new hybrid representative selection technique developed by U-SPEC aims to find a balance between the efficiency of random selection and the effectiveness of k -means based selection. Then, to rapidly construct a bipartite graph between the original data objects and the set of representatives, a new approximation approach for K -nearest representatives is proposed, on which the transfer cut can be used to produce the clustering result. In the ensemble creation step, numerous U-SPECs are used to generate an ensemble of diverse and high-quality base clusterings.

ADVANTAGES:

1. Capable of Robust Partitioning
2. Efficient for Large data sets

DISADVANTAGES:

1. Work only on specific shaped cluster
2. Cannot Identify Outliers and Identifiers
3. Works on Restricted Data which has motion at center.

TIME COMPLEXITY:

Time Complexity of U-SPEC is $O(n)$

D. DISTRIBUTION -BASED CLUSTER SELECTION

Distribution based cluster structure framework used to find the most representative unified cluster structure.

The technique or a strategy has been designed namely Distribution -based cluster structure selection strategy(DCSS) to select a subset of the clusters structures. DCSE works on the real-world datasets. The following diagram shows how the DCSE works in general. This paper makes a five-fold contribution. To begin, a number of distribution-based distance functions are used to compare the similarity of two Gaussian distribution sets.

Second, present a DCSE framework for determining the unified cluster structure in an ensemble of various cluster structures. Finally, a distribution-based cluster structure selection strategy (DCSSS) is used to pick a subset of the ensemble's acceptable cluster structures. The distributionbased hypergraph normalised cut algorithm, in turn, is aimed to find the best representative cluster structure. Fifth, use a nonparametric test to assess the difference between the two groups.

Fig3: Overview of DCSE approach[17]

The DCSE framework, which is aimed to determine the most representative unified cluster structure, and the DCSSS, which is designed to choose a subset of cluster structures in the ensemble, are both included in this research.

1) The cluster structure is represented by DCSE as a blend of Gaussian distributions produced using the EM method.

- 2) The similarity of two sets of Gaussian distributions is measured using a set of DDMs.
- 3) The DCSSS is used to increase DCSE's performance.
- 4) To choose the best representative cluster structure, the distribution-based hypergraph normalised cut algorithm is utilised.

E. A NOVEL ALGORITHM FOR INITIAL CLUSTER CENTER SELECTION

In this paper, a new cluster centers selection method ICCS K means is proposed, focusing on the artificial determination of the number of clusters K and randomness of the initial centers selection, as well as the question of whether the result converges to the local minimum rather than the global minimum. The optimal number of clusters K is calculated using the distance cost function F

(S, K) and the distance cost minimum criterion in our technique. In addition, by specifying density and distance, the initial cluster centers are automatically selected.[18]

Initial Center Clusters normal procedure is discussed below:

Number of clusters K and data set D with n data objects as inputs.

K initial cluster centers are the output.

- 1: Determining the d-distance between any two objects;
- 2: Considering each object in data set D as a cluster center and calculating the r of its MNN (the repetition distance is only counted once);
- 3: Calculating the average of all r, abbreviated as \bar{r} ;
- 4: Calculating the density of each data object in the \bar{r} neighbourhood
- 5: Multiplying each object's density by the corresponding distance \bar{r} , indicated as f.
- 6: Sorting f from highest to lowest;
- 7: The top K values are the initial cluster centers;
- 8: Calculate the distance between each object and each cluster center for each of the remaining n K objects, and assign each object to the nearest cluster.

The standard K means clustering approach is heavily reliant on the number of clusters K and initial cluster centers chosen, and if the number of clusters and initial cluster centers chosen are insufficient, the clustering results may lose their stability. A method for determining the number of clusters K is presented, as well as a new way for locating cluster centers is presented in the paper. The clustering process is effectively improved with this method, which uses MNN, density, and distance to find the initial cluster centers. Experiments show that the algorithm has a high level of robustness.

III. SUMMARY OF THE PAPERS

Sr No.	Name of the Paper	Publication Detail	Proposed Conceptualization	Research Possibility	Tools and Technologies Used
1.	Hierarchical Density Based-Clustering using MapReduce	(Published in IEEE Transactions on Big Data, Vol7, No1, January-March 2021)[2]	1)Efficient for large datasets. 2)Proposed a Parallelization scheme recursive Sampling.	1)Parallelization of HDBSCAN* for shared memory architectures.	1)10 machines connected with local ethernet. 2)Cluster was configured with Apache Spark 2.1.1 with Hadoop 2.7 over Linux
2.	Unsupervised K-means Algorithm	(Published in IEEE Access, Vol 8, April,2020)[13]	1)Finding an optimal number of clusters without giving any initialization and parameter selection	1)To work on complicated geometrical shape clusters	1)All Algorithms are implemented on MATLAB2017db.
3.	Ultra-Scalable Spectral Clustering and Ensemble Clustering	(Published in IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering ,VOL.32,NO.6,JUNE2020) [1]	1)Two large scale algorithms which shows the scalability and robustness for large data sets clusters.	1)To identify the noise more efficiently and could work on different shapes clusters	1)for an experiment evaluation all algorithms are implanted on MATLAB
4.	Distribution- Based Cluster Structure Selection.	(Published in IEEE transactions on Cybernetics, Vol47, November,2017)[17]	1) how to choose the most appropriate cluster structures in an ensemble, which will then be summarised into a more representative cluster structure.	1)To perform DSCE algorithm more on the real world applications.	1)20 real datasets from the University of the California and DSCE framework.
5.	A Novel Algorithm for initial cluster center Selection	(Published in IEEE Access, VOL7,2019)[18]	1)To select fast initial cluster centers with an algorithm.	1)To perform algorithm which can be more time and cost efficient	1)12 groups of typical benchmark data sets and applied in spectral data of LAMOST

IV. CONCLUSION:

To apply **hierarchical density-based clustering** to huge datasets quickly using MapReduce, recursive sampling is a novel parallelization strategy that computes an estimated clustering hierarchy based on a significantly faster.

On a variety of datasets, the suggested method is assessed in terms of runtime and approximation quality, demonstrating its effectiveness and scalability.

For optimal number of clusters to discard the extra clusters and the **U-k means clustering** are free of

initializations and any number of clusters can be found with respect of any shape and data size.

For the large scalable datasets starting from ten thousand and ranging to ten million the **Ultra-Scalable Spectral Clustering and Ensemble Spectral Clustering** must be used. For ensembling multiple structure into one unified structured cluster the **Distribution based Structure Algorithm** plays a vital role.

By the use of Mnn, a novel algorithm for initial center cluster selection the centers of the cluster can be chosen with less difficulty and create an ease to know efficiency of the clustering.

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A review on machine learning approach for plant disease detection

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Abstract—In an agriculture-centered country like India plants are our primary produce and hence making sure that they are up to the mark and are not affected by any diseases. Moreover, with our rapidly increasing population and needs we require to take measure to reap as much as we sow. Hence, we need to make sure the prevailing diseases are detected as fast as they can be so we can take the necessary measures. Machine learning and image processing algorithm are the easiest way for disease detection in plants as they take the help of an image dataset for recognizing the plant disease. In this paper we study various methods used for disease detection in various plants.

Keywords—Plants, Machine learning, Classification, Image processing, disease.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian economy relies heavily on agriculture and hence it is very necessary to make sure that the quality and quantity of the yield is up to the mark. The prevailing diseases affecting the plants are one of the biggest problems faced by the farmers. The diseases affect the plants in a large scale. it results in the whole stock being unusable. it results in wastage of time resources and finances. So, it is an issue which should be aptly deal with.

Indian farming still widely uses traditional approach for a lot of things. Technology while being now introduced and used in comparatively larger scale than previous decade is still not as prevalent as it should be. So, generally the method used. In order for plant disease detection is a farmer's observation which relies highly on gut instinct, experience and limited knowledge hence, it is not accurate. Further once the farmer is vary of infection in plants he/she contacts the experts in order to know for sure and take necessary measures which further results in time wastage.

Hence, in order to make disease detection in plants easier, handy and timely a machine learning approach can be used. The use of image processing and classification in order to study the plants based on a pre prepared database seems the easiest and fastest way to approach the issue. The pre prepared dataset contains necessary information about the diseases and helps in its classification. It is more accurate than a farmer's gut instinct and faster than contacting the expert and going through tests in the case where urgent actions are required. After the detailed study we conclude to approach the problem with machine learning, CNN architecture for feature extraction gives most optimal results.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various research have been done in the past and this paper studies a few number of those in detail in order to study the techniques used for disease detection in plants.

In paper [1] the researchers have developed an android application with the help of android studio and android SDK tools which recognizes 5 disease anthracnose, black Band-die black, soft rot and stem rot and their system has four major functionalities: image capturing which mean the farmer captures the image of the infected region ,uploading the bitmap image to the server by the farmer with the help of AsyncTask class, downloading the result of whether the plant infected and with what ailment and then last getting solution where the farmer is directed to solution.xml where they can control and view the solution provided by the Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI). The most important task of the disease detection which in their case focuses on the jute plant stem is done by image processing. at first the image is resized to match the image size of the database, after the resizing it is enhanced by contrasting and using 1% of all pixels then noise removal is done by bilateral smoothing filter and then hue-based segmentation to separate the infected region of stem also a threshold formula is used and then to make things easier RGB image is converted to HSV image and thresholding is performed and the resulted masked image with threshold as 0.5 pixel is further amplifies with blob segmentation for removal of unwanted image and then finally the HSV image is converted to original RGB color. Then feature extraction is performed with help of color co-occurrence methodology by GLCM. The features extracted are compared to pre-prepared dataset in .mat file and a SVM classifier is used which uses supervised learning method.

The system contains two .mat files training data and result. The training dataset contains 150 rows 13 columns and result contains 1 row and 13 columns.

Fig. 1. a) Hue, b) Saturation and c) Intensity Image [1]

Fig. 2. e) Masked Image, f) Segmented Blob, g) Segmented RGB Image [1]

The testing is done by two cases with hue-based segmentation with 86% accuracy and without hue-based segmentation with 60% accuracy overall and hence they decided to go with hue-based segmentation. This system can only be used for stem disease and further scope is to develop the system to detect leaf diseases too.

In paper [2] the researchers' study various supervised machine learning techniques for maize leaf disease detection and compare the resultant accuracy to find the best approach. The first method considered is naïve bayes in which the pattern are known because of prior probabilities and the class label are the assumed posterior probabilities the class label calculates which case is most probabilistic it is done by product of conditional probability of each feature. This hypothesis may not hold in real environment as efficiently it is a pretty popular method. The next method considered is KNN (K nearest neighbor) it is based on nearest neighbors rule in it the resulted class label is derived from most commonly assigned classes to nearest neighbors, the outcomes are different till end as it depends on assumptions. The training is done with the help of matching test dataset to train dataset. The next method is used is decision tree in which data is divided into much smaller sets with the help of entropy for selection of attributes. The decision tree is very easy to understand and produces very less training error. It has ID3, C4.5, CART as commonly used methods for implementation. SVM is the most commonly used method for disease detection purpose. In high dimensional space the separable features are extracted further general functions are used to transform features it increases the margin between label and optimizes the process but increases dimension of features space and training time. The last approach considered is Random Forest (RF) in which multiple decision trees are constructed during training. The class label particularly for testing depends on classification tree voting. The main aim is to create a forest of decision trees which are as uncorrelated as possible in order for most possible accuracy.

The image dataset is picked directly from plant village website it contains images for common rust, gray leaf spot, northern leaf blight and healthy having 3823 images in total. The acquired data is then preprocessed by removing noise and converting original images to greyscale and resizing the images to smaller and optimal sizes. Further image segmentation is performed with the help of similarities in which predefined criteria is used or discontinuities which uses sudden changes in intensity. These steps are followed by feature extraction in which color, texture and shape are used

as major features. The experimental results show SVM, NB, KNN, DT, RF give 77.56, 77.46, 76.16, 74.35 and 79.23 in percentage respectively. The paper concludes that RF gives the most accuracy. So, in the case of supervised learning RF is our best bet.

In paper [3] describes a smartphone application for disease detection in rice plant. The images taken by the smartphone are sent to cloud sever which contains a training dataset and with the help of it classification of disease is performed and the server sends the image back to smartphone to display it.

The whole application is divided into major two parts cloud sever application made with the help of python with flask and smartphone part made with react native cross platform android system. The dataset contains 1600 images from Kaggle. The data pre-processing contains noise removal, image size reduction and image segmentation. The whole model works on CNN model. The feature extraction, where color shape and texture are extracted as feature is followed by backpropagation training to reduce errors. The VGG16 deep learning model based on CNN architecture and has 16 weighted layers. During testing the data is preprocessed and then passed through trained model and is finally classified into either of four classes brown, hispa, leaf blast and healthy.

Fig. 3 The architecture of smartphone application for detecting rice plant disease [3]

The dataset of 1600 and out of which 20% (320) are used for testing and the data segmentation is done using candy edge method. Training was done using 100 epoch and 0.0001 learning rate. They observed that the losses reduced significantly after 38th epoch. The train accuracy was observed 100% and while test accuracy was 60% and kept fluctuating till last. It can easily be optimized by increasing testing data size which could be a future prospect.

In paper [4] proposes a new framework based on deep learning, spectral domain uses band pass filtering as algorithm in which different regions are represented with

different bandwidth. The high bandwidth can be used for more texture level learning and lower bandwidth can be used for edges and corner.

The images are acquired with the help of sensors. The acquired images are preprocessed by removing image distortion, geometric transformation, the color is enhanced, image clipping is done to separate infected part smoothing filter is used for image smoothing. Then image segmentation is performed with the help of canny algorithm to make image easier to understand. Then feature extraction is performed using CNN based model. While the accuracy is not mentioned the dataset contains 10,000 images and 80% is used training and 20% is used for testing. This particular model works for 79 diseases for 14 different species of plant

This is a web-based portal and further scope relies in developing IOS and android application and further accuracy can be worked with.

III. CONCLUSION

In this paper I have reviewed various methods that rely on machine learning and image processing for the purpose of disease detection in various parts of various species of plant. India has always prided itself for its agriculture growth and being as our maximum population relies on agriculture for income, the yield being affected by disease and becoming disposable is a major problem. The present method most commonly used is a farmer's naked eye and then further expert opinion once approached by farmer, this process is not only time consuming but also unreliable. So, a automated approach is a great alternative. Different method for feature extraction gives different accuracies, out of all the approach the two papers [3] and [4] that used CNN approach give the most accuracy and diversity in disease to be detected and plants. Moreover, CNN being a deep learning approach

makes it easier for implementation. The CNN based system makes sure to optimize the training error as much as possible and even the testing error can also be optimized if we take enough large dataset.

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A Review on Protein Structure Classification Based On Distance Feature

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Abstract— In Bioinformatics field Protein Structure Classification is the most important task. The known proteins have been classified based on their level, feature, function, amino acid and family and superfamily. Protein structure divided in to four types: all- α protein structure, all- β protein structure, $\alpha+\beta$ protein structure and α/β protein structure. Use of traditional way to perform classification is very difficult and time-consuming task. Number of advanced Machine Intelligence computing techniques like Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Artificial Neural Network, Decision Tree and Naïve Bayes Classifier had been proposed in the literature. Our objective in this research paper is to develop a system that performs better than previous predictors for protein structure classification by considering the distance among the different amino acid residues. To examine the performance of proposed work different datasets will be used.

Keywords— Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Artificial Neural Network, Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes Classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

Proteins are essential nutrients for the human body. They are one of the building blocks of body tissue and can also serve as a fuel source. They are like machines that make all living things, whether viruses, bacteria, butterflies, jellyfish, plants, or human function. The human body consists of around 100 trillion cells. Each cell has thousands of different proteins. Together, these cause each cell to do its job. The proteins are like tiny machines inside the cell.

Fig. 1. Primary Structure

Fig. 2. Secondary Structure

Fig. 3. Tertiary Structure

Fig. 4. Quaternary structure

Proteins are made up of hundreds or thousands of smaller units called amino acids, which are attached to one another in long chains. There are 20 different types of amino acids that can be combined to make a protein, amino acids like A, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, V, W, Y. Proteins are likewise significant basic constituent of cells in organism. There are four degrees of protein structures viz. Primary

Structure [Fig.1], Secondary Structure [Fig.2], Tertiary Structure [Fig.3], Quaternary Structure [Fig.4].

II. RELATED WORKS

Babasaheb Satpute, Dr. Raghav Yadav they proposed protein arrangement figured the separation of every amino acid residue from the residue. At that point took the mean of all separations of a specific amino acid residue from first residue. Prepare a dataset of size 600X 20 it means for each protein there are 20 features and 600 total number of proteins In[1].

Loris Nannia,n, Sheryl Brahname, Alessandra Luminib propose a new machine learning system that is based on combining several protein descriptors extracted from different protein representations, such as position specific scoring matrix (PSSM), the amino-acid sequence, and secondary structural sequences. The prediction engine of our system is operated by an ensemble of support vector machines (SVMs), where each SVM is trained on a different descriptor In[4].

Naveenkumar K S, Mohammed Harun Babu R, Vinayakumar R, Soman KP mainly focus on the related works done previously on protein classification using deep learning. Using Natural language processing which mainly focus on biological sequence, the features are been extracted using n-gram, Bio-vec and Prot-v to identify the protein structure and classified into different structure for which deep neural network has been implemented to find n-dimensional vectors In[5].

Fatima KABLI, 1st Fatima KABLI, Reda Mohamed HAMOU, Abdelmalek AMINE present a global frame work inspired by the knowledge extraction process from biological data based on the association rules. This framework has three main steps: the pre-processing phase consists of extracting the descriptors, they used the N-Gram technique, second is devoted to extracting the association rules between the proteins components, applied the Apriori algorithm; As a third step we selected the relevant rules to classified the unclassified protein. And tested this classifier on five classes of protein, extracted from the uniprot data bank compared with five methods of classification in WEKA platform, based on the validation tools and obtained satisfied results improve the effectiveness of their protein classifier In[3].

Wenzheng Bao, Yuehui Chen, Dong Wang proposed a new method to predict the tertiary structure of the protein, the method by extracting the protein sequence of the amino acid frequencies generalization dipeptide information hydrophobic combination, using neural networks and flexible neural tree classifier for different the integrated structure classification model .To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed method and choose two benchmark protein sequence datasets (640 dataset and 1189 dataset) as the test data set. The final results show that our method is efficient for protein structure prediction In[6].

Wenzheng Bao, Dong Wang and Yuehui Chen proposed Flexible neutral tree (FNT), a particular tree structure neutral network, has been employed as the classification model in the protein structures' classification framework. Considering different feature groups owing diverse roles in the model, impact factors of different groups have been put forward in this research. In order to evaluate different impact factors, Impact Factors Scaling (IFS) algorithm, which aim at

reducing redundant information of the selected features in some degree, have been put forward. To examine the performance of such framework, the 640, 1189 and ASTRAL datasets are employed as the low-homology protein structure benchmark datasets In[2].

Ashish Ghosh, Bijan Parai made an attempt to map the protein secondary structure prediction problem as pattern classification problem and used three different low cost pattern classification techniques for solving it. We used minimum distance, K-NN and fuzzy K-NN classifiers, among which minimum distance produced the best results for window size 11. Between the other two, fuzzy K-NN gave better performance with window size 3. We also varied the value of K, better results were achieved in the range. Experiments are conducted using different percentage of training sets and the findings were similar In[12].

III. DIFFERENT METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

Biological database that is composed of a large collection of computerized ("digital") nucleic acid sequences, protein sequences, or other polymer sequences stored on a computer. The mission of UniProt is to provide the scientific community with a comprehensive, high-quality and freely accessible resource of protein sequence and functional information. Now, there are almost 8 million sequences in a nonredundant (NR) database of protein sequences, including the complete genomes of $\approx 1,800$ different species. It has data header include Entry, Organisms, Protein Gene, Family, amino acid Sequence, Length etc.

B. Feature Extraction

- Distance features

Extracted features for every protein sequence in each family. In each protein sequence compute the distance of each amino acid residue from the first residue. Then take the mean of all distances of a particular amino acid residue from first residue. For example if a residue 'A' occurs 14 times in a particular sequence, then for 'A' we will get 14 distances for 'A' i.e. for every occurrence of 'A' will compute its distance from the first residue. Then take the mean of those 14 distances, which will be the feature value for 'A'. Thus for every protein sequence we will get 20 feature values as there are 20 different amino acid residues which occur multiple times in a sequence. Prepare a dataset of size 600 X 20 i.e. for each protein there are 20 features and 600 total number of proteins.

- Parameter features

These following features are novel designed: A. $\text{Ratio}_{EC} = \text{Num}(E)/\text{Num}(C)$ and $\text{Ratio}_{HC} = \text{Num}(H)/\text{Num}(C)$, where Num (E), Num (H) and Num (C) stand for the counts of E, H and C, respectively. B. The percent of α -helices $(\text{Count_Seg_H} / \text{L_seq})$ and β strands $(\text{Count_Seg_E/L_seq})$ in predicted protein structure sequence. C. The percent of α -helices $(\text{CountSegH/L_strand\&helix})$ and β -strands $(\text{CountSegE/L_strand\&helix})$ in E-H sequence. D. The Variance of α -helices length (Var_seg_H/L_seq) and β -strands length (Var_seg_E/L_seq) in predicted protein structure sequence. E. The Variance of α -helices length $(\text{Var_seg_H} / \text{L_strand\&helix})$ and β -strands length

(Var_seg_E /L_strand&helix) in E-H sequence. F. The Second order composition moment of EH and HE (represented by Com_Moment_seq_EH and Com_Moment_seq_HE) in predicted protein structure sequence. G. The Second order composition moment of EH and HE (represented by Com_Moment_strand&helix and Com_Moment_strand&helix) in E-H sequence. H. The Variance of the positions of E (Var_Pos_E-seq) and positions of H (Var_Pos_H-seq) in predicted protein structure sequence. I. The Variance of the positions of E (Var_Pos_E_strand&helix) and positions of H (Var_Pos_H_strand&helix) in E-H sequence. J. The Frequency of ww (noted by fww) in E-H sequence, where ww = EH, HE. K. The Normalized difference of Count_Seg_E in predicted protein structure sequence and E-H sequence. L. The Normalized Lempel-Ziv (LZ) complexity of both predicted protein structure sequence and E-H sequence, where LZ complexity is proposed by Lempel and Ziv in 1976 [39] M. The average interval of ww in sequence which is defined as

$$Avg_In_ww = \begin{cases} \frac{P_{ww}(N(ww)) - P_{ww}(1)}{N(ww) \times L_strand \& helix}, N(ww) \neq 0 \\ 0, N(ww) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

ww=EH, HE, E (i) and H (i), where i ranges from 1 to 20. So we can take an example of a protein structure that only has 20-length amino acids among them. The sequence showed as below: EEEHHHHEEEHHHEEEEE. Taking advantage of the Ave_In method, the parameter of corresponding number show: PHH= (4, 5, 6, 12, 13), N (HH)=5, PHH (1)=4. E (k) and H (i) represent the i-word which includes i continuous E and H, respectively. For instance, E (4)=EEEE and H (2)=HH.

- Association rules

Faced with enormous number of extracted rules, we have been brought to the original problem of data mining. The question asked; how to extract the important and significant rules RS for the manipulation and decision making in the classification step? Consequently; we must follow an effective strategy to select the significant rules among exists ones. Depending on the problem addressed in our case and the different methods of selecting the significant rules we keep the association rules with the following characteristics.

The rules written in the form $X \rightarrow Class$; Such that the right part (consequence) defines the items of the class attribute (in the purpose of selecting the adaptive rules with the classification problem, which allowed us to predict the class of an unknown protein):

An association rule Ra: $A \rightarrow C$ is more general than another association rule Rb: $B \rightarrow C$ if $A \subset B$ // Therefore, Ra is more significant than Rb:

- Position specific scoring matrixs

Initially introduced by Gribskov et al. (1987) for the purpose of detecting distantly related proteins, PSSM5 is generated from a group of sequences previously aligned by structural or sequence similarity and takes into consideration the following four parameters:

Position: the sequentially increased index of each amino acid residue in a sequence after multiple sequence alignment;

Probe: a group of typical sequences of functionally related proteins that have been aligned by sequence or structural similarity;

Profile: a matrix of 20 columns corresponding to the 20 amino acids;

Consensus: the sequence of amino acid residues that is most similar to all the alignment residues of probes at each position.

Formally, the PSSM representation for a given protein sequence of length N is an Nx20 matrix, where each element PSSM(i,j) is

$$PSSM(i, j) = \sum_{k=1}^{20} w(i, k) \times Y(j, k) \quad (2)$$

where $i \in [1, \dots, N]$, $j \in [1, \dots, 20]$, $w(i, k)$ is the ratio of the frequency of appearance of the kth amino acid (considering the 20 amino acids) at position i of the probe and the total number of probes, and $Y(j, k)$ is the value of Dayhoff's mutation matrix between the jth and kth amino acids (i.e., $Y(j, k)$ is a substitution matrix).

- Multi-scale local descriptor

This technique is used to divide protein sequence into multiple sequence segments of varying length to describe overlapping local regions. In here, continuous sequence segments are composed of residues which are local in the polypeptide sequence. A sequence contains continuous region and discontinuous region. In this study, only continuous regions are used, and discontinuous regions discard.

Firstly each protein sequence is replaced by the index depending on its grouping. We consider a sequence "QQNHHHNNQNNNQHHQQNNQHQ" is replaced by 11322233133312211333121 based on this classification of amino acids. There have eight '1', six '2' and eight '3' in this protein sequence. The construction of these three symbols is composed of the equations,

For calculating the value of distribution D, if there are n residue in a protein sequence. Then position for 1st residue is (0% * n) and position for 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th residue is (25% * n), (50% * n), (75% * n) and (100% * n) respectively. The three descriptors (C, T and D) are calculated for each local region and joined, and a total of 63 descriptors are formed as 7 for C, 21 ((7*6)/2) for T and 35 (7*5) for D. By that way 63 dimensional vectors from 63 descriptors for each protein sequence formed. Three descriptors are calculated and joined, and total 63 features are generated.

Single input protein sequence in the dataset:

```
MPQIQSSHSNHFDFTIDTADRTKLLMSYLVVPTTA
NFNNVMHGGELLNLLDKVAYVCSTRYCAKGTVTLVS
DGVTFKYPIPVGNLLTFLASINYVGNTSCEVGIKVLSE
DIKTREITHNTNSCYFTMVAVENGKPTPMPKYEPKTEV
EIRRYEGAL
```

C. Classification

- Support vector Machin

A Support Vector Machine algorithm is to find a hyperplane in an N-dimensional space (N — the number of features) that distinctly classifies the data points.

Fig. 5. SVM Classification Hyper Plan

To separate the two classes of data points, there are many possible hyperplanes that could be chosen. Our objective is to find a plane that has the maximum margin, i.e. the maximum distance between data points of both classes. Maximizing the margin distance provides some reinforcement so that future data points can be classified with more confidence.

- Naive Bayes

Using Bayes theorem, we can find the probability of A happening, given that B has occurred. Here, B is the evidence and A is the hypothesis. The assumption made here is that the predictors/features are independent. That is presence of one particular feature does not affect the other. Hence it is called naive.

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A)P(A)}{P(B)} \quad (3)$$

- K- Nearest Neighbour

An object is classified by a majority vote of its neighbors, with the object being assigned to the class most common among its k nearest neighbors (k is a positive integer, typically small). If k = 1, then the object is simply assigned to the class of that single nearest neighbor.

Fig. 6. KNN Classification Cluster

- Artificial Neural Network

Artificial Neural Network ANN is an efficient computing system whose central theme is borrowed from the analogy of biological neural networks. ANNs are also named as “artificial neural systems,” or “parallel distributed processing systems,” or “connectionist systems.” ANN acquires a large collection of units that are interconnected in some pattern to allow communication between the units. These units, also referred to as nodes or neurons, are simple processors which operate in parallel. Every neuron is connected with other neuron through a connection link. Each connection link is associated with a weight that has information about the input signal. This is the most useful information for neurons to solve a particular problem because the weight usually excites or inhibits the signal that is being communicated. Each neuron has an internal state, which is called an activation signal. Output signals, which are produced after combining the input signals and activation rule, may be sent to other units.

- Decision Tree

A decision tree is a map of the possible outcomes of a series of related choices. It allows an individual or organization to weigh possible actions against one another based on their costs, probabilities, and benefits. They can be used either to drive informal discussion or to map out an algorithm that predicts the best choice mathematically. A decision tree typically starts with a single node, which branches into possible outcomes.

Fig. 7. Decision Tree Structure

IV. COMPARATIVE STUDY

TABLE I. FEATURE EXTRACTION METHOD

Method	Advantage	Limitation
Distance [1]	-Simple Calculation -Easy to implement -batter accuracy	-Amino acid in pattern is require.
Parameters []	-Numerical output -Easy to store	-Complex to implement
Association	-Significant rules among exists ones	- Eenormous number of extracted rules
Position Specific Scoring Matrix	-Easy Calculation	-Less accurate
Multi-scale local descriptor	- Describe overlapping local regions	-Large Feature Dimension

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION METHOD

Method	Advantage	Limitation
NB [1]	Fast to train. Fast to classify. Handles real and discrete data Handles streaming data well	Strong feature independence assumption.
NN	NN can perform tasks which linear program cannot. When element of neural network fails it continue to work.	They do not classify and cluster data, a lot of chips and a distributed run-time to train on very large datasets.
SVM	SVM is less complex. Produce very accurate classifiers. Less over fitting, robust to noise.	SVM is binary classifier, to do a multi-class classification, pair-wise classifications can be used Computationally expensive, thus runs slow
Decision Tree	+It reduces overfitting and is therefore more accurate. +Easy to Implement works with all types of data. +Multi classification Support.	-It may not work if the dependent variables considered in the model are linearly related. Therefore, one has to remove correlated variable by some other technique
KNN	-Robust to noisy training data -Effective if the training data is large	-Distance based learning is not clear which type of distance to use and which attribute to use to produce the best result. -computation cost is quite high

CONCLUSION

Protein structure prediction is the inference of the three-dimensional structure of a protein from its amino acid sequence. In this research studied about different structures

of protein all- α , all- β , $\alpha+\beta$ and α/β and their features extraction methods. Researches are based amino acid features factor scale, association, Apriorist rules etc. For classification they uses SVM, NB, DT and ANN classification approaches. So, In future if we work on distance combination feature (n-gram) with random forest classier give batter output for classification.

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Gesture Recognition for Home Automation

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Abstract—Gesture recognition is a topic of computer science which is used for interpreting human gesture. Gesture can be originate from any bodily motion or state but commonly originate from face and hand. In this paper, we propose a method to recognize gestures using machine learning.

Keywords—gesture recognition, transfer learning, CNN, sensor data

I. INTRODUCTION

Gesture recognition provides real-time data to a computer to make it fulfill the user's commands. Motion sensors in a device can track and interpret gestures, using them as the primary source of data input. A majority of gesture recognition solutions feature a combination of 3D depth-sensing cameras and infrared cameras together with machine learning systems. Machine learning algorithms are trained based on labeled depth images of hands, allowing them to recognize hand and finger positions.

One of the most common applications of gesture recognition is home automation. Home automation means to control and use the home appliances automatically. This work using the fast algorithm for identifying hand gestures.

II. GESTURE RECOGNITION FOR HOME AUTOMATION

Here, we defined six types of gestures or motions to control home devices as below:

As shown in Figure horizontal grip and moving up and down is for TV ON and OFF. Vertical grip and moving up and down is to turn and off the air conditioner. Turning left and right is for light ON and OFF.

For the gesture recognition, we use transfer learning with a CNN model that has been developed by Google using 1,000 categories of large imageset from ImageNet. It can be trained and classify our input data using the pre-trained model. In this research, we retrain the final layer of the CNN model.

The gesture is acquired using a smartphones with sensor is stored in a file, which is converted into images for training and testing using transfer learning.

III. WORK FLOW OF THE SYSTEM

For the vision-based hand gesture recognition method, which we described via an algorithm, there were distinct stages in the system we proposed and created—the gesture recognition flowchart of the operation as shown in Figure.

The suggested algorithm of hand gesture recognition has the following steps.

1. From the recorded video stream, extract a frame, that is, a hand image.
2. The extracted frame is converted from the color space of RGB to the color space model of YCbCr. Then using skin color-based detection techniques, the hand is detected in the image.
3. The machine transformed the picture into black and white after hand recognition (i.e., the skin pixels were identified as white and nonskin pixels as black). Some preprocessing strategies, such as picture filling, morphological erosion utilizing 15×15 structuring elements, etc., were implemented to enhance image clarity and eliminate noise.
4. The equivalent diameter, field, perimeter, and orientation of detected objects are found in the frame for the function extraction centroid. All the

features were used before we had the nonconflicting production.

5. The gesture is recognized by counting the number of white items in the picture and its direction. Lastly, an instruction is transmitted to the device's programs, referring to the known motion.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we discussed the method to recognize gestures using sensor data from a sensor. We defined six types of gestures, and we used transfer learning. As an application, we can use it for home automation to control home appliances and the system which requires a touchless user interface.

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A Review on Machine Learning in Healthcare

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Abstract - In the past few years, there has been a significant development in the healthcare and various industries where Machine Learning plays an important role. This report aims to analyze and to utilize the full potential of Machine Learning initiatives in the healthcare industry.

Keywords - Machine learning, Healthcare, Artificial intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare sector has long been an early adopter of and benefited greatly from technological advances. These days, machine learning (a subset of artificial intelligence) plays a key role in many health-related realms, including the development of new medical procedures, the handling of patient data and records and the treatment of chronic diseases. Machine learning has virtually endless applications in the healthcare industry. Today, machine learning is helping to streamline administrative processes in hospitals, map and treat infectious diseases and personalize medical treatments.

The implementation of Machine Learning (ML) in the health sector reflects promising opportunities for considerably improving the delivery of healthcare. Private healthcare businesses are considering the development

of ML in the process of decision making, adopting tools for supporting physicians and other medical fields. Algorithms can be developed specifically for their independent functions across the medical industry. Several researchers in the medical field are exploring ML tools for the analysis of big data as the future of this industry is considerably changing. ML is simply enhancing the smartness of the healthcare industry.[1]

This paper aims to critically analyse the implementation of ML in the healthcare industry by understanding how ML is revolutionizing the industry and what its full potential is for the industry.[1] However, recently, machine learning has been identified as having major technological application in the healthcare realm. While such technologies will probably never completely replace physicians, they can transform the healthcare sector, benefiting both patients and providers.[2]

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

In today's connected world, data across sectors are growing exponentially. As the volumes of data increase, new novel ways to interact with and to extract meaning from the data are emerging.[2] The innovative use of machine learning technologies combining small and big data analytics will support a better provisioning of healthcare to citizens.[3] Machine learning can prove to be the solution for both reducing the rising cost of healthcare and helping establish a better patient-doctor relationship.[2] The machine learning different algorithms will help us to find out hidden patterns and meanings from the collected data. Machine learning uses the mainly two approaches one is supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

The realm of supervised learning involves training algorithms using particular examples. The machine receives a number of inputs with a given number of correct outputs; the learning occurs by comparing empirical results with the correct outputs to identify errors. This type of learning is used when past history can be used to predict events in the future.[2] An example is to classify patients into either diseased or healthy. A domain expert (eg, a physician) assigns an annotation (the "label"), for example, diseased or healthy, to every patient. The aim is to find the model that best distinguishes between those two classes, to either correctly assign the label diseased or healthy to new, unlabeled patients, or to identify important covariables. Problems of this kind are called classification problems (Fig. 1).[4]

Fig 1: Illustration of a classification task; a model learns to separate diseased from healthy individuals in a 2-dimensional space.[4]

The other approach is unsupervised learning. Under this approach, the machine must explore the data and attempt to develop some sort of pattern or structure; it must develop models from scratch and is not told any correct outputs. This method is often used to pinpoint and distinguish outliers.[2] The goal in unsupervised learning problems is to find patterns and to extract hidden structure from data, completely data driven without any expert labelling. Typical examples are clustering problems that aim to group similar data points together (Fig. 2).[4]

Fig 2: Illustration of an unsupervised clustering task; a model finds similar data points and groups them together.[4]

There are a number of industry and research initiatives that aim to apply machine learning technology in the healthcare realm in order to improve the lives of patients around the world . The first of which is a research laboratory based out of Stanford University in Palo Alto, CA. The Shah Lab is headed up by Dr. Nigam Shah and is part of the center of Biomedical Informatics Research at Stanford. The researchers at the Shah Lab use machine learning and data mining in medical ontologies “to enable the learning health system.” The researchers look at Electronic Health Records that include longitudinal data regarding patient care—what is important to note is that this initiative analyzes unstructured data.[2] By looking at patterns for what has been done before in medicine in the large scale, the lab attempts to answer clinical questions, generate data driven insights, and build predicative models regarding the progression of disease, the effectiveness of treatments, and the processes of medical care. All of these insights, the Shah Lab believes, will help doctors make better decisions. Additionally, the lab’s insights have impacts in other areas of the healthcare realm. Their pharmacovigilance methods can flag adverse drug events early even before drug recalls. They have also found that androgen deprivation therapy, a treatment for prostate cancer, can actually increase the chance of developing Alzheimer’s disease.[2] Another initiative that is gaining traction in the healthcare sector is Lumiata, a healthcare startup specialized in graph analytics. Lumiata is headed by Dr. Igor Barani and was recently named by MIT technology review as one of the top 50 smartest companies of 2016. Enlitic, another startup company, is utilizing deep learning and machine learning to harness a new era of data-driven medicine. The key is to turn medical data such as lab x-rays and images, patient histories, and

physician notes into meaningful insights and patterns. In a nutshell, it compares medical images to large datasets of past images and data to offer incredibly valuable and accurate insights to physicians. It is important to note that this certain software offers accuracy, efficiency, and transparency. The doctor always understands and is made aware of the reasoning behind all the technical insights. Recently, it was found that Enlitic technology detected lung cancer nodules in chest CAT Scan (CT) images 50 percent more accurately as compared to an expert panel of radiologists. This sort of technology can prove to be vital in lowering healthcare costs and helping doctors provide a more personalized, patient centered approach to medicine.[2]

In a prototypical, retrospective study based on electronic medical records data from the University of Michigan Hospitals and the Massachusetts General Hospital, Oh et al20 used a datadriven approach to build hospital-specific models to estimate daily patient risk for Clostridioides difficile infection (CDI) using L2 regularized logistic regression. These machine-learning models were built and internally validated based on data from >150,000 adult admissions and involved several thousand time-invariant and time-varying variables; they resulted in a good predictive performance with areas under the receiver operating characteristic curve ranging from 0.75 to 0.82. At both institutions, the models identified half of true-positive cases at least 5 days prior to diagnosis of CDI. As part of a surveillance or decision support tool, these models could help to rapidly identify new cases of CDI, before microbiological test become available, or to select patients who should be tested for the presence of CDI.[4]

BenevolentAI: BenevolentAI was founded in 2013 by Ken Mulvany founder of

Proximagen. BenevolentBio is focused on applying technology in the bioscience industries. The initial focus has been on human health – generating new ideas that have the potential to improve the lives of millions and deliver better medicines to patients faster in currently overlooked areas such as orphan disease and rare cancers. BenevolentTech is developing an advanced artificial intelligence platform that helps scientists make new discoveries and redefines how scientists gain access to, and use, all the data available to drive innovation. The technology is built upon a deep judgement system that learns and reasons from the interaction between human reasoning and data.[2]

Butterfly Network: Butterfly Network is transforming diagnostic and therapeutic imaging with devices, deep learning, and the cloud. Butterfly Network operates at the intersection of engineering and medicine by bringing together world-class talent in computer science, physics, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering and medicine.[2]

III. CONCLUSION

Healthcare is one of the fastest growing sector in the today's economy; more people require health care so it is becoming more expensive day by day. Government is also spending more money and funding in healthcare sector to improvise the medical facilities in terms of cost and provides the better care to the patients. Technologies like Machine learning, Big data and AI have the potential to help both patients and providers in terms of better care and lower costs. A number of companies and organization have already taken the first step in this industry and have helped facilitate the transition to patient and evidence-orientated care.

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A survey on intelligent spam email detection

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Abstract— In this digital era, with the increasing use of smartphones and social networks, online communication has become a part of daily life. Email is convenient and essential for professional and personal use. With rapid use of emails, spam email becomes the bigger problem, demanding the intelligent system to filter spam email to save time, improve efficiency and security of e-mail communication. This survey paper presents the recent research for spam email detection using Artificial Intelligence and machine learning techniques with different parts of an email's structure such as email headers, email body and email attachments. In this paper, different methods from current research are identified, summarized. Also, discussing challenges and providing insightful information to work in the future for this area.

Keywords— Spam email detection, Intelligent spam email filtering, machine learning, email classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Email has become the way of communication in daily life in the emerging technological world. It is also used for enhancing authentication for different shopping, educational and social network sites. So that some emails are not useful, that is known as spam emails which are sent out for marketing, Hoaxes, money scams, online dating, data breach, email spoofing, malware warnings etc.[1] This emails needs to filter out from usual email for improving the user experience and preventing cyber-attacks. In recent research, researchers identified different artificial intelligence methods to classify spam emails intelligently. Using various parts of emails, each approach may perform better or worse, depending on the data provided. This can be achieved by NLP techniques, deep learning models, and machine learning models.

An email contains the body and header. The email body can be text, images, audio, or video. Email headers contain information that is unstructured and mainly used for security purposes. The general structure of the intelligent spam email detection system is shown in fig1. The spam classifier shown in the figure describes the model with different methodology using various parts of emails.

The aim of this paper is to outline the current research in this area and give future directions to researchers who are interested in working on intelligent spam email detection. Section II describes the related work of spam email classification. Section III is about discussing and analyzing the various approaches for classifying emails. Section IV is giving the future direction in current research along with the conclusion.

Fig1. Base model for email classification

II. RELATED WORK

Spam as an unwanted message which can be used for fraud or scam. There are several researches done in spam filtering using different machine learning classifiers, NLP based system and also using deep learning models. With current research in the field, researchers identified email content and header both as an important feature to detect spams.

Email Content: To, From, subject and body text. By applying various pre-processing techniques, feature extraction techniques and then processing with different classifiers to classify the emails.

Email Headers: Email headers have various features such as cc, Bcc, X-mailer, Received, Return-path, message-ID etc. With base header features and derived header features [2] (from the base feature to detect spam), analyzing the effect of various feature and then applied artificial intelligence technique to do classification of email effectively.

III. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we will discuss the analysis and performance from the literature review. In Table 1, we provide the summary and additional comments from current research which can be helpful in identifying future directions. This table contains information about the dataset used, approach mentioned, results obtained in literature. Also, the last column about additional comments is used for improving the current methodology or enhancing into new methodology.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF SPAM DETECTION

Literature	Dataset	Approach	Classification Technique	Results	Additional comments
Effect of Header based Features on Accuracy of Classifiers for Spam Email Classification[2]	Personal Emails Spam Assassin CSDMC 2010	Detecting spam email with various header features	Naïve Bayes Decision Tree Random Forest SVM Naïve Bayes Tree	With minimum 5 and maximum 14 features, random forest works better	Enhancing the performance of model using other header features.
Header Based Email Spam Detection Framework Using Support Vector Machine (SVM) Technique[3]	Anomaly Detection Challenge CSDMC 2010	Extract the basic header feature and applied SVM	SVM	SVM works well with both datasets used in experiment	Apply different algorithms to improving the results.
Email Spam Detection Using Machine Learning Algorithms [4]	Kaggle(spam.csv)	Data pre-processing done by stop words, tokenization and bag of words	SVM K- Nearest Neighbor Naïve Bayes Decision Tree Random Forest Ensemble methods	Multinomial Naïve Bayes gives the best outcome and Ensemble methods proven to be useful	Filtering of spams can be done on the basis of the trusted and verified domain names.
Classification Spam Email with Elimination of Unsuitable Features with Hybrid of GA-Naive Bayes[5]	dataset collects from Hewlett-Packard (HP) laboratory	GA algorithm is employed for the feature selection	GA - Naïve Bayes	GA-Naïve Bayes has a better performance than naïve bayes	Proposed method can be tested on standard larger dataset
Machine Learning based Spam E-Mail Detection[6]	Ling spam dataset	Introduced hybrid bagged approach for email	Naïve bayes J48 Hybrid bagged approach	Experimental results are better when performed on only J48 algorithm	To enhance the system's performance and results, the concept of boosting approach can be applied
A Proposed Data Science Approach for Email Spam Classification using Machine Learning Techniques[7]	Enron email dataset UCI email dataset	Three-tier architecture proposed using email header and content	Probability model based on decision theory	Self-learning system implication for both individuals and organizations	Make a system capable enough to learn in diverse environment.
Comparison of Deep and Traditional Learning Methods for Email Spam Filtering[1]	Enron email dataset SMS spam collection	Deep learning techniques CNN and LSTM model with(out) a GloVe model proposed	Traditional machine learning classifiers Deep learning classifiers	Deep learning classifiers, random forest and xgboost classifiers produce improved results than the traditional classifiers	Classifier can be improved by using a combination of deep learning classifiers based on text and image spams.

It is observed from almost all papers that authors have chosen to apply various algorithms on email body text. Also, monitored from literature that naive bayes, the machine learning algorithm performs better with text classification.

IV. FUTURE SCOPE AND CONCLUSION

By analyzing current research in this area, we have summarized the details in table 1. This comparative study of spam email detection using email text and headers will be very beneficial for the community. As there is a rapid increment in online communication, detecting spam email is crucial. Although there is much research done and ongoing in this field, no algorithms or methods have an 100% efficiency.

Here are some of the keys to work in future on spam email detection: As with text classification we got higher accuracy but at the same time spammers also got to update their text from time to time. For the same, we can have some system that can detect the spam email by text dynamically. By using email headers, it is a more secure way to detect the spam email as we have more information that is hidden in headers. So, one can find a more reliable header feature which can lead us to improve accuracy of the system. Also, we can build a system that can stop sending detected spam emails to the end user. And at last, researchers can build a hybrid system using email body text classification and using email header to detect the spam emails. Additionally, email attachments also can be used for classifying emails.

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